

Addition to the main text
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Proposition:

Let $u \in \overline{R(K)}$, $Ju = 0$. Then, $u = 0$ holds.

Proof:

There exists a sequence $\{g_n\}_n$ in L such that $\lim_n \|Kg_n - u\|_H = 0$ holds.
 $\|u\|_H^2 = \lim_n \langle Kg_n, u \rangle_H = \lim_n \langle g_n, Ju \rangle_L = 0$ holds. ■